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MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF FLOW INDUCED BY A ROTATING DISK AND CORE IN A CYLINDRICAL RESERVOIR WITH TANGENTIAL INLET AND RADIAL OUTLET

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Abstract

The present study investigates the flow in a stationary cylindrical reservoir induced by a rotating disk driven by a central shaft together with a coaxial rotating rod (core). In contrast to the classical von Kármán problem, which considers flow near an infinite rotating disk, the proposed model accounts for finite system dimensions, sidewalls, tangential inflow, and localized radial fluid outflow. The presence of the rotating core forms an annular flow region and significantly modifies the angular momentum distribution, swirl structure, and spatial organization of the flow. It is shown that the combined action of disk and core rotation, axial inflow in the annular region, centrifugal radial ejection, and pressure gradients generated by fluid outflow leads to the formation of a complex three-dimensional multicellular flow. The resulting structure includes primary and secondary recirculation zones, separatrix surfaces, spiral vortex structures, and tertiary vortex formations. A mathematical approach is proposed for determining separatrices and critical points of the stream-function field, making it possible to establish the conditions for tertiary vortex formation and the loss of axial symmetry. Special attention is devoted to the tertiary vortex, which is interpreted not as a localized compact vortex core, but as a distributed multilayer spiral-conical structure developing along separatrices and shear layers surrounding the rotating core. It is shown that the tertiary vortex regime represents an intermediate stage between stable axisymmetric circulation and complex unsteady vortex motion. The obtained results generalize the classical von Kármán rotating-disk flow model to the case of a confined cylindrical domain with an internal rotating boundary as well as external sources and sinks of momentum. It is established that the interaction of swirl generation, viscous diffusion, recirculation, and localized fluid outflow leads to the formation of a vortex structure that cannot be described within the framework of the classical self-similar theory of rotating-disk flow.

Keywords: rotating disk, cylindrical reservoir, viscous incompressible fluid, Navier–Stokes equations, swirl flow, recirculation zones, vortex structure, tangential inlet, radial outlet, secondary flows, Reynolds number, meridional circulation

1. Introduction. Flows in rotating fluids represent one of the classical areas of hydrodynamics and have been extensively investigated both theoretically and experimentally. One of the most well-known models is the von Kármán problem describing the flow near an infinite rotating disk, for which a self-similar solution was obtained, characterizing the boundary-layer structure, radial transport of fluid, and axial inflow toward the disk surface [1]. Further development of this theory was associated with the works of Cochran [2], Prandtl and Tietjens [3], Batchelor [5], as well as modern studies of boundary layers and swirling flows [4, 8–10].

In rotating-disk systems, angular momentum transport, viscous stresses, and the interaction between radial, azimuthal, and axial velocity components play a fundamental role. In confined domains, the flow structure becomes significantly more complicated due to the influence of sidewalls, finite geometry, and external boundary conditions [11–13]. Under such conditions, closed recirculation zones, secondary flows, and complex vortex structures arise as a result of vorticity redistribution and the breakdown of axial symmetry [14–17].

Particular interest is associated with swirling flows involving both inflow and outflow of fluid. The presence of localized suction generates low-pressure

regions, deformation of streamlines, and intense shear layers. Munro and Foster [7] demonstrated that non-axisymmetric drainage in a rotating reservoir can substantially reorganize the global vortex structure and lead to the formation of complex three-dimensional flow regimes.

Despite the considerable number of studies, the spatial organization of vortex structures in systems with simultaneous rotation, tangential inflow, and localized outflow remains insufficiently understood. In particular, little attention has been devoted to regimes involving tertiary vortex structures formed in regions of intense shear between major recirculation zones. Unlike classical localized vortices, such structures possess a distributed spatial character and are associated with the global reorganization of the flow.

In the present work, the flow in a cylindrical reservoir with a rotating disk, a coaxial rotating rod (core), tangential inflow, and radial outflow of fluid is investigated. The presence of the rotating core forms an annular flow region and significantly modifies the angular momentum distribution and swirl structure in the near-axis region. It is shown that the interaction of centrifugal radial ejection above the disk, axial inflow in the annular region, core rotation, and localized pressure

gradients leads to the formation of a complex multicellular flow structure.

A mathematical approach is proposed for determining separatrices of recirculation zones and analyzing the conditions for tertiary vortex formation. It is shown that the tertiary vortex does not represent a localized vortex core, but rather a spatial multilayer spiral-conical structure developing along separatrices and shear layers between the principal circulation regions. The obtained results may therefore be regarded as a generalization of the classical von Kármán rotating-disk model to the case of a confined cylindrical domain with an internal rotating boundary and external sources and sinks of momentum.

2. Problem formulation. A steady flow of a viscous incompressible fluid in a stationary cylindrical reservoir is considered, induced by a rotating disk of finite radius and a coaxial rotating vertical rod. The study focuses on a high-Reynolds-number flow regime, where inertial effects dominate in the bulk of the flow, while viscous stresses are confined to thin boundary layers near solid surfaces. In addition, the flow is driven by a tangential inflow of fluid, generating swirl, while fluid removal occurs through a radial outlet in the sidewall. Such a configuration leads to the formation of a complex three-dimensional flow combining rotation, radial mass transport, and axial circulation. The reservoir has radius R and height H , the disk has radius b , the rod radius is r_s , and the angular velocity of the disk and rod is Ω . The fluid is characterized by density ρ and kinematic viscosity ν .

At height $z = z_d$ within the reservoir, a rotating disk of radius b is located. The fluid is supplied through a tangential inlet and removed through a radial orifice of radius a in the sidewall.

A cylindrical coordinate system (r, φ, z) is used, where the z -axis is directed perpendicular to the plane of the disk. The computational domain is an annular region $r_s \leq r \leq R, 0 \leq z \leq H$, since the inner region $0 \leq r < r_s$ is occupied by a solid rotating rod. The velocity field is specified as $\mathbf{u} = (u_r(r, z), u_\varphi(r, z), u_z(r, z))$, and the pressure is $p = p(r, z)$.

The fluid motion is governed by the Navier–Stokes equations for an incompressible medium. The continuity equation takes the form

$$(1/r)(\partial(ru_r)/\partial r) + \partial u_z/\partial z = 0 \quad (1)$$

The radial component of the momentum equation is written as

$$u_r(\partial u_r/\partial r) + u_z(\partial u_r/\partial z) - (u_\varphi^2/r) = -(1/\rho)(\partial p/\partial r) + \nu(\Delta u_r - (u_r/r^2)) \quad (2)$$

The azimuthal component takes the form

$$u_r(\partial u_\varphi/\partial r) + u_z(\partial u_\varphi/\partial z) + (u_r u_\varphi/r) = \nu(\Delta u_\varphi - (u_\varphi/r^2)) \quad (3)$$

and the axial component is written as

$$u_r(\partial u_z/\partial r) + u_z(\partial u_z/\partial z) = -(1/\rho)(\partial p/\partial z) + \nu \Delta u_z \quad (4)$$

On the surface of the rotating disk ($z = z_d, r_s \leq r \leq b$), the no-slip boundary conditions are imposed:

$$u_r = 0, u_z = 0, u_\varphi = \Omega r. \quad (5)$$

On the surface of the rod ($r = r_s$)

$$u_r = 0, u_z = 0, u_\varphi = \Omega r. \quad (6)$$

On the stationary walls of the reservoir:

$$u_r = 0, u_\varphi = 0, u_z = 0. \quad (7)$$

Fluid outflow occurs through a radial outlet in the sidewall:

$$r = R, z \approx z_d \quad (8)$$

The mass flow rate through the outlet is defined as

$$Q = \int_{S_{out}} u_r dS, \quad (9)$$

or, in approximate form,

$$Q \approx u_r(R, z_d) S_{out}. \quad (10)$$

In contrast to the classical problem of an infinite rotating disk, the system considered has finite dimensions, is bounded by walls, contains fluid inlet and outlet, and also has an internal rotating boundary. In the general case, this excludes a self-similar transformation, and the problem must be considered in the full formulation for partial differential equations. Nevertheless, near the disk surface, the flow retains the properties of a boundary layer and can be approximated by the von Kármán self-similar solution. A dimensionless variable is introduced as

$$\zeta = z\sqrt{\Omega/\nu} \quad (11)$$

and the velocities are represented in the form

$$u_r = r\Omega F(\zeta), u_\varphi = r\Omega G(\zeta), u_z = \sqrt{\nu\Omega} H(\zeta). \quad (12)$$

Here, the functions $F(\zeta), G(\zeta)$, and $H(\zeta)$ satisfy the von Kármán system of equations. This representation is applicable locally and is used to estimate the boundary-layer thickness, shear stresses, and angular momentum transport. The vorticity field is defined as

$$\boldsymbol{\omega} = \nabla \times \mathbf{u} \quad (13)$$

with components given by

$$\begin{cases} \omega_z = (1/r)(\partial(ru_\varphi)/\partial r), \\ \omega_r = -\partial u_\varphi/\partial z, \\ \omega_\varphi = (\partial u_r/\partial z) - (\partial u_z/\partial r). \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

In the vicinity of the disk, an intense vortex structure is formed with a dominant axial component. Within the reservoir volume, redistribution of vorticity occurs, leading to the formation of closed recirculation zones. The characteristic boundary-layer thickness is estimated as $\delta \sim \sqrt{\nu/\Omega}$, and the flow regime is determined by the Reynolds number

$$Re = \Omega b^2/\nu. \quad (15)$$

Physically, the flow develops as follows. The rotation of the disk and the rod imparts azimuthal momentum to the fluid, which within the disk radius is transformed into a radial outflow. In accordance with the continuity equation, an axial inflow toward the disk arises, forming in the annular region $r \gtrsim r_s$. Near the surface of the rod, an additional boundary layer develops, enhancing the swirl in the central part of the flow. In a confined volume, this mechanism leads to the formation of a closed circulation pattern, including a downward flow in the near-axis annular region, radial outflow above the disk, upward motion along the sidewall, and the return of fluid toward the central region in the upper part of the reservoir. As a result, a system of secondary recirculation zones is formed, separated by separatrices, along which regions of intensified shear arise, providing conditions for the formation of smaller-scale vortex structures.

3. Mathematical model.

Substitution of the self-similar velocity representations (12) into the Navier–Stokes equations in the

boundary-layer approximation leads to the following system of ordinary differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} 2F + H' = 0, \\ F^2 + F'H - G^2 - F'' = 0, \\ 2FG + HG' - G'' = 0, \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

The first equation expresses the law of mass conservation in the boundary layer and establishes the relation between the radial and axial velocity components:

$$H' = -2F. \quad (17)$$

This means that the radial outflow of fluid is accompanied by an axial inflow toward the disk surface. In the considered system with a rotating rod, this inflow is formed not on the axis $r = 0$, but in the annular region $r \gtrsim r_s$, since the central part is occupied by a solid body.

The second equation

$$F^2 + F'H - G^2 - F'' = 0 \quad (18)$$

describes the radial momentum balance. The term F^2 corresponds to inertial effects, $F'H$ to momentum transport in the axial direction, G^2 to the action of centrifugal forces, and F'' to viscous resistance. In the presence of a rotating rod, the radial flow distribution near the center changes; however, in the local region $r \gtrsim r_s$, the structure of the balance remains similar to that in the classical problem.

The third equation

$$2FG + HG' - G'' = 0 \quad (19)$$

characterizes the transport of azimuthal momentum. The terms $2FG$ and HG' describe angular momentum transport by the radial and axial flows, whereas G'' reflects viscous decay of rotation. The presence of the rod enhances swirl in the central region, increasing the azimuthal velocity near the inner boundary and changing the global distribution of the function $G(\zeta)$; however, within the boundary layer, the structure of the equation remains unchanged.

It should be emphasized that this self-similar representation is applicable only in the local region near the disk surface. In a system with finite geometry, sidewalls, a rotating rod, tangential inflow, and radial outflow, self-similarity is violated, and the global flow is not described by system (16). Outside the boundary layer, the flow structure is determined by the interaction of radial ejection, axial inflow in the annular region, rod rotation, sidewalls, and inlet/outlet boundary conditions, which leads to the formation of a complex multicellular vortex structure.

The functions $F(\zeta)$, $G(\zeta)$ and $H(\zeta)$ describe the radial, azimuthal, and axial velocity components near the disk, respectively. The boundary conditions on the disk surface are given by

$$F(0) = 0, G(0) = 1, H(0) = 0, \quad (20)$$

which corresponds to the absence of radial slip, the equality of the azimuthal fluid velocity to the disk velocity, and the impermeability of its surface. Far from the disk, in the classical problem, the conditions

$$F(\infty) = 0, G(\infty) = 0, \quad (21)$$

are imposed; however, in the present system these conditions are only approximate due to the influence of external boundaries.

The system (16) does not admit an analytical solution and is solved numerically as a boundary-value problem. Within the framework of this model, its solution is used to determine local boundary-layer characteristics, including velocity distributions and the value of the derivative $G'(0)$.

The shear stress on the disk surface is defined as

$$\tau_{z\varphi} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_\varphi}{\partial z} \right)_{z=0}, \quad (22)$$

from which, taking into account the self-similar representation, it follows that

$$\tau_{z\varphi} = \rho r \Omega \sqrt{\nu \Omega} G'(0). \quad (23)$$

This expression remains valid in the presence of the rod, since it is determined by the local properties of the flow near the disk surface. Integration over the surface of the disk of radius b gives an estimate of the torque:

$$M \sim \rho \Omega^2 b^4 \sqrt{\nu \Omega}. \quad (24)$$

In the presence of the rod, the magnitude of the torque may change due to flow redistribution and enhanced swirl in the central region; however, the functional dependence on the parameters ρ, b, Ω and ν is preserved.

In the general case, the pressure is not a function of the self-similar variable alone and is determined from the Navier–Stokes equations taking into account geometry and boundary conditions. Formally, it may be represented as:

$$p = \rho \nu \Omega P(\zeta), \quad (25)$$

however, near the disk the radial pressure gradient is governed by centrifugal forces:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \sim (\rho u_\varphi^2) / r. \quad (26)$$

This leads to an increase in pressure from the inner region of the flow toward the periphery. In the presence of the rod, the pressure distribution in the central zone is determined by the boundary conditions at $r = r_s$, where the rotation of the solid boundary maintains an elevated level of swirl.

In the vicinity of the disk surface, an intense vortex structure is formed with a dominant axial component of vorticity, which determines the spiral character of the streamlines. The radial component is associated with the variation of the azimuthal velocity in the direction normal to the disk, while the azimuthal component is related to shear effects arising from the interaction of radial and axial motions. Near the surface of the rod, a region of increased vorticity also develops, enhancing rotation in the near-axis zone.

In contrast to the classical problem, the flow exhibits a pronounced three-dimensional character. In the boundary layer at the disk, maximum velocity gradients and high vorticity intensity are observed; a similar but more localized layer forms at the rod surface. Within the reservoir volume, momentum redistribution and attenuation of swirl occur, accompanied by the formation of closed recirculation zones. In the region of radial outflow, the flow accelerates, which is accompanied by a local pressure decrease and deformation of streamlines. The tangential inflow enhances the swirl, and in the presence of the rod this effect becomes more pronounced. For sufficiently strong inflow, a region close

to quasi-solid-body rotation is formed, in which the azimuthal velocity depends only weakly on the radius within the annular zone $r \gtrsim r_s$.

Numerical results show that the azimuthal velocity reaches its maximum near the disk and the rod surface and decreases with height; the radial velocity is directed from the inner region toward the periphery in the disk region and changes sign in the return-flow region; the

axial velocity forms a downward flow toward the disk in the near-axis annular zone and an upward motion along the sidewall. The vortex lines have a spatially spiral structure and connect the region of the rotating disk and rod with the peripheral outflow zone, forming a complex circulation system.

Figure 1. Schematic of the experimental setup: a cylindrical reservoir with a rotating disk and a coaxial rotating rod, tangential fluid inflow, and radial outflow through a side opening. On the left, a projection of the main streamlines in a meridional section is shown: the fluid entering tangentially descends in the near-axis annular region toward the disk, then, under the action of centrifugal forces, spreads radially toward the walls and rises upward, forming a closed circulation loop. On the right, a top view is presented, illustrating the spiral nature of the motion on the disk: the streamlines take the form of diverging spirals, reflecting the combined action of radial outflow and azimuthal rotation.

4. Numerical simulations. Numerical investigation of the flow was carried out for a stationary cylindrical reservoir with a finite rotating disk and a coaxial rotating rod, tangential inflow, and radial outflow of fluid. In contrast to the classical von Kármán problem, the system under consideration is characterized by finite geometric dimensions, the presence of sidewalls, an internal rotating boundary, and localized inlet and outlet. Therefore, a strictly self-similar representation of the flow throughout the entire reservoir is not applicable. In this work, the von Kármán solution is used as a local asymptotic model near the disk surface, whereas the global flow structure is described in terms of the stream function field in the meridional plane of the annular region $r_s \leq r \leq R$.

The system of equations is solved numerically using the finite volume method on a structured grid with second-order accuracy. Pressure–velocity coupling is achieved using the SIMPLE algorithm. The flow regime is determined by the Reynolds number (15).

The calculations were performed for water with kinematic viscosity $\nu = 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, reservoir radius $R = 0.50 \text{ m}$, height $H = 0.50 \text{ m}$, disk radius $b = 0.13 \text{ m}$, rod radius r_s , disk position $z_d \approx 0.06 \text{ m}$, and angular velocity of the disk $\Omega = 100 \text{ rad/s}$. The disk was considered finite and occupied the region $r_s \leq r \leq b$. The reservoir remained stationary; therefore, Coriolis forces were neglected. The swirl of the fluid was generated by the rotation of the disk and rod, as well as by the tangential inflow.

To describe the meridional motion, a stream function $\psi(r, z)$ was introduced, through which the velocity components were defined as

$$u_r = (1/r)(\partial \psi / \partial z), u_z = -(1/r)(\partial \psi / \partial r) \quad (27)$$

This representation automatically satisfies the continuity equation (1).

The stream function field was constructed as a superposition of contributions corresponding to the main physical mechanisms of the flow: the downward axial motion toward the disk, radial outflow above the finite disk, upward motion along the sidewall, localized suction in the outflow region, and closed recirculation cells. The contribution of radial outflow was confined to the region $r \leq b$, reflecting the finite size of the disk, while the inner boundary $r = r_s$ excludes flow in the central region and introduces additional rotational influence.

The characteristic dimensionless parameters of the problem were defined as

$$Re_\Omega = \Omega R^2 / \nu, S = U_{in} / \Omega R, C_Q = Q / \Omega R^3. \quad (28)$$

For the selected parameters, $Re_\Omega = 2.5 \times 10^7$. When estimated based on the disk radius $b = 0.13 \text{ m}$, one obtains $Re_\Omega = 1.69 \times 10^6$, which corresponds to a strongly inertial flow regime in which centrifugal transport and swirl play a dominant role, while viscous effects are primarily confined to boundary layers. The thickness of the local viscous layer near the disk is estimated using the von Kármán scale as

$$\delta \sim \sqrt{\nu / \Omega} = \sqrt{10^{-6} / 100} = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}.$$

A boundary layer of the same order of magnitude is formed near the surface of the rod. Unlike the infinite-disk case, this estimate characterizes only a local region, whereas in the reservoir volume the flow is governed by interaction with boundaries and global circulation.

Figure 2. Vertical profiles of the dimensionless velocity components and vorticity for the flow induced by a finite rotating disk and a coaxial rotating rod in a cylindrical reservoir with tangential inflow and radial outflow of fluid. The plots illustrate the influence of the rod on the enhancement of swirl in the near-axis region, the redistribution of axial flow in the annular zone, and the variation of the vortex structure with height.

The numerical results show that near the disk a radial outflow of fluid is formed from the inner boundary toward the periphery, limited by the radius b . Above the disk, a transitional conical region arises in which the downward flow from the near-axis annular zone turns into the radial direction. Along the sidewall, an upward flow is formed, closing the global circulation. In the central and upper parts of the reservoir, large recirculation zones develop, while near the outflow region a localized suction zone and deformation of streamlines are observed. The rotating rod enhances the swirl in the near-axis region and significantly affects the position and shape of the recirculation zones.

A characteristic feature is the presence of several critical points of the stream function, defined by the conditions $u_r = 0, u_z = 0$, or equivalently

$$\partial\psi/\partial r = 0, \partial\psi/\partial z = 0.$$

In their vicinity, streamlines close upon themselves, forming recirculation zones. Saddle points define separatrices that separate regions of circulation. Along these lines, increased velocity gradients are observed, creating conditions for the formation of tertiary vortex structures.

Physically, the obtained results reflect the mechanism of flow formation in a confined volume under the action of a rotating disk and rod. The rotation imparts

azimuthal momentum to the fluid, which in the vicinity of the disk is transformed into a radial flow directed toward the periphery. In accordance with the continuity equation, a compensating axial flow directed toward the disk is formed in the annular region. This flow is involved in a closed circulation loop, including downward motion in the near-axis zone, radial outflow above the disk, upward flow along the sidewall, and return of the fluid to the inner region in the upper part of the reservoir. The tangential inflow and radial outflow further deform the flow structure.

The shear stress on the disk surface is determined by the local characteristics of the boundary layer and can be estimated based on the von Kármán solution:

$$\tau = \rho r \Omega \sqrt{\nu \Omega} G'(0).$$

Thus, the von Kármán solution remains applicable as a local asymptotic model describing the flow behavior near the disk. At the same time, in a confined volume with a rotating rod, tangential inflow, and radial outflow, the global flow structure is governed by the interaction of recirculation zones, boundary conditions, and system geometry, leading to the formation of a complex three-dimensional vortex system.

Figure 3. Profiles of the velocity components and streamline structure for the flow induced by a finite rotating disk and a coaxial rotating rod in a cylindrical reservoir. The influence of the rod on flow redistribution is shown: the formation of radial outflow above the disk in the annular region, the displacement of the descending axial flow from the axis toward the region $r \gtrsim r_s$, and the development of a system of closed recirculation zones. The streamlines demonstrate a complex circulation pattern resulting from the interaction of rotation, sidewalls, and fluid inflow and outflow.

5. Recirculation regions on the disk. On the surface of the rotating disk, the streamlines are not purely radial. Physically, a fluid particle near the disk simultaneously participates in azimuthal rotation and undergoes radial transport from the center toward the periphery. Thus, the velocity has two components: a radial component $u_r > 0$ and an azimuthal component $u_\phi = \Omega r$, and can be written as

$$\mathbf{u} = u_r \mathbf{e}_r + u_\phi \mathbf{e}_\phi \quad (29)$$

Consequently, the motion of particles near the disk surface is not radial but helical (spiral) in nature. In projection onto the plane of the disk, the streamlines form diverging spirals directed from the inner region toward the periphery, while simultaneously rotating in the direction of disk motion (Figs. 1 and 4). The particle trajectory in polar coordinates is determined by:

$$d\varphi/dr = u_\phi/ru_r, \quad (30)$$

which shows that the degree of swirl is determined by the ratio of azimuthal to radial velocity.

Using the von Kármán solution self-similar representation [1]:

$$u_r = r\Omega F(\zeta), u_\phi = r\Omega G(\zeta), \quad (31)$$

we obtain

$$d\varphi/dr = G(\zeta)/r F(\zeta). \quad (32)$$

Near the disk surface, the function $G(\zeta)$ takes relatively large values, whereas $F(\zeta)$ remains finite; therefore, particle trajectories are strongly twisted. As the distance from the disk increases, the azimuthal velocity decreases, leading to a reduction in the spiral character of the streamlines.

Thus, a correct representation of the flow on the disk should exhibit diverging spiral streamlines rather than a purely radial flow. Similarly, near the bottom of the reservoir, the streamlines retain a weak spiral character due to angular momentum transport. Although the radial velocity component is directed from the inner region toward the periphery, the overall particle trajectories remain spiral.

6. Transverse (horizontal) recirculation regions in the tank.

To describe recirculation regions in a transverse cross-section of the reservoir, consider the plane

$z = z_k = \text{const}$, perpendicular to the axis of rotation. Due to the presence of a coaxial rotating rod, the flow domain is an annular region $r_s \leq r \leq R$, since the inner part $r < r_s$ is occupied by a solid body.

In this plane, the fluid motion is described by two velocity components $u_x(x, y, z_k)$ and $u_y(x, y, z_k)$, which are projections of the radial and azimuthal velocities onto Cartesian axes. The transformation from cylindrical to Cartesian coordinates yields

$$\begin{cases} u_x = u_r \cos \varphi - u_\phi \sin \varphi, \\ u_y = u_r \sin \varphi + u_\phi \cos \varphi. \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

Using the von Kármán solution self-similar representation

$$\begin{cases} u_r = r \Omega F(z), \\ u_\phi = r \Omega G(z), \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

we obtain the velocity field in the transverse plane as:

$$\begin{cases} u_x = r\Omega F(z_k) \cos \varphi - r\Omega G(z_k) \sin \varphi, \\ u_y = r\Omega F(z_k) \sin \varphi + r\Omega G(z_k) \cos \varphi. \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

In the vicinity of the disk, radial outflow and azimuthal rotation occur simultaneously, resulting in spiral particle trajectories. In the general case, the velocity components u_r and u_ϕ depend on the radial coordinate and height and are determined by the global flow structure. For analysis, a two-dimensional stream function $\chi(x, y; z_k)$ is introduced, defined by

$$u_x = \partial\chi/\partial y, \quad u_y = -\partial\chi/\partial x. \quad (36)$$

The curves $\chi = \text{const}$ represent streamlines in the transverse plane. The centers of recirculation zones are determined by the conditions:

$$u_x = 0, \quad u_y = 0. \quad (37)$$

or equivalently

$$\partial\chi/\partial x = 0, \quad \partial\chi/\partial y = 0. \quad (38)$$

Thus, each recirculation region corresponds to a critical point of the function χ , around which the streamlines are closed. The vorticity in the transverse section is determined by the axial component

$$\Omega_z = (\partial u_y/\partial x) - (\partial u_x/\partial y). \quad (39)$$

A change in the sign of Ω_z indicates the presence of neighboring vortex regions with opposite directions of rotation.

In the problem under consideration, the velocity field is formed by the combined action of several mechanisms:

$$\mathbf{u}_{\perp} = \mathbf{u}_{disk} + \mathbf{u}_{rod} + \mathbf{u}_{in} + \mathbf{u}_{out}. \quad (40)$$

The contribution of the rotating disk describes radial outflow and swirl:

$$\mathbf{u}_{disk} = u_r \mathbf{e}_r + u_{\varphi} \mathbf{e}_{\varphi}, \quad (41)$$

where $u_r > 0$ in the disk region. The rotating rod generates additional swirl in the near-axis region:

$$\mathbf{u}_{rod} = \Omega r \mathbf{e}_{\varphi}, \mathbf{r} \approx \mathbf{r}_s, \quad (42)$$

which leads to an enhancement of azimuthal motion and a displacement of the flow toward the annular region. The tangential inflow generates a supply of angular momentum:

$$\mathbf{u}_{in} = U_{in} \mathbf{e}_{\varphi}, \quad (43)$$

while the radial outflow creates a localized suction region, which in the first approximation may be described as a planar sink:

$$\mathbf{u}_{out} = -(Q/2\pi h)((\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{out})/|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{out}|^2). \quad (44)$$

Here $\mathbf{x} = (x, y)$, \mathbf{x}_{out} denotes the position of the outlet, Q is the flow rate, and h is a characteristic layer thickness.

In each transverse section, an individual system of recirculation zones is formed. Near the disk, radial outflow and swirl dominate; therefore, the streamlines exhibit a diverging spiral pattern. Due to the presence of the rotating rod, the flow develops not at the center but in the near-axis annular region $r \gtrsim r_s$, where enhanced swirl and flow around the inner boundary are observed.

In the middle part of the reservoir, the contribution of radial outflow decreases, and the flow structure becomes more ordered, approaching a ring-like motion around the rod. The recirculation zones take the form of weakly deformed annular regions.

In the upper part, the return flow from the sidewall toward the inner region is intensified, and the influence of the tangential inflow becomes more pronounced. This leads to a displacement of the recirculation centers, deformation of the annular structures, and redistribution of vorticity. The swirl weakens but is maintained due to the rotation of the rod and residual angular momentum.

Thus, transverse sections at different heights reflect the three-dimensional evolution of the vortex field: from intense spiral motion near the disk and rod, to a more ordered annular flow in the middle part of the reservoir, and further to return circulation in the upper region. Such a structure cannot be fully described by a longitudinal section alone.

Transverse sections make it possible to identify the distribution of swirl, the location of local centers of rotation, and the geometry of annular recirculation regions in planes perpendicular to the axis of rotation. This is particularly important for understanding the

three-dimensional organization of the flow, in which the spiral nature of motion is determined by the combined action of radial and azimuthal velocity components, as well as by the influence of the internal rotating boundary.

Figure 4 shows transverse sections of the reservoir at different height levels. The main recirculation zones are highlighted by color, and the streamlines illustrate the structure of fluid motion in each plane. The inner region is occupied by a rotating rod of radius r_s , and therefore the flow develops in the annular domain $r_s \leq r \leq R$. The presented sections make it possible to trace the spatial evolution of the flow, including changes in swirl intensity, redistribution of radial and axial velocity components, and the displacement and deformation of recirculation zones under the combined influence of disk and rod rotation, tangential inflow, and radial outflow of the fluid.

In the lower cross-section, located near the rotating disk ($z = 0.055m$), the flow structure is governed by the direct influence of the disk and the coaxial rotating rod. Since the inner region is occupied by a solid body, the flow develops in the annular zone surrounding the rod. In this region, intense swirl is observed, and the streamlines exhibit a pronounced spiral character due to the combined action of radial outflow, azimuthal rotation, and flow around the inner boundary. The flow is directed from the near-axis annular region toward the periphery, while maintaining a high angular velocity. Near the sidewall, a return flow is formed, giving rise to an outer recirculation zone. The radial outflow through the sidewall induces asymmetry in the velocity field and creates a localized suction region on the right-hand side of the cross-section.

In the cross-section at $z = 0.140m$, the influence of the rotating disk weakens; however, the swirl maintained by the coaxial rotating rod persists in the near-axis annular region. The streamlines become more organized and approach closed trajectories. A stable annular region is formed, in which azimuthal motion dominates. The asymmetry caused by the tangential inflow and radial outflow remains, but is less pronounced than in the vicinity of the disk.

In the middle cross-section ($z = 0.280m$), the radial velocity component decreases significantly, and the flow structure is governed primarily by azimuthal motion, return circulation, and vorticity redistribution. The streamlines form a large swirling region around the rod, with the center of the recirculation zone shifted relative to the geometric center of the reservoir. This shift is associated with the influence of tangential inflow, radial outflow, and the internal solid boundary.

Figure 4. Recirculation zones in transverse cross-sections of a stationary tank with a rotating disk.

In the upper cross-section ($z = 0.420\text{m}$), the radial outflow induced by the disk nearly vanishes, and the flow is dominated by return motion in the upper part of the reservoir. The swirl weakens significantly but does not disappear completely due to the influence of the rotating rod and tangential inflow. The streamlines become less spiral and reflect the return of fluid toward the inner annular region. As a result, a system of weak recirculation zones is formed, corresponding to the upper part of the global circulation.

Thus, the transverse sections demonstrate a gradual transformation of the vortex structure: from intense spiral motion near the disk and rod, to a more ordered annular flow in the middle region of the reservoir, and further to return flow in the upper region. The presence of a coaxial rotating rod prevents flow through the axis $r = 0$, displaces the near-axis flow into the annular region $r \gtrsim r_s$, and enhances swirl near the inner boundary, significantly affecting the formation and spatial organization of recirculation zones.

In the upper sections, a change in the orientation of spiral streamlines is observed compared to the near-disk region. This is associated with a change in the sign of the radial velocity component as the flow transitions from radial outflow to return flow, leading to a corresponding change in the sign of $d\varphi/dr$ and reflecting the three-dimensional structure of the circulation.

7. Secondary recirculation regions (downward flow) in the meridional section. The mathematical explanation of the formation of secondary recirculation zones in the considered rotating reservoir follows from the Navier–Stokes equations in cylindrical coordinates

under the simultaneous action of several factors: a rotating disk, a coaxial rotating rod, tangential inflow of fluid, and radial outflow through a side opening.

These mechanisms generate competing directions of momentum transport: the disk induces radial outflow of fluid, the rod enhances swirl in the near-axis region, the tangential inflow supplies additional angular momentum, and the radial outflow creates a localized low-pressure region. As a result, the flow loses a simple axisymmetric structure and breaks into several closed circulation cells.

Let the velocity field be written as

$$\mathbf{u} = (u_r, u_\varphi, u_z) \quad (45)$$

For an axisymmetric formulation, the continuity equation takes the form

$$(1/r)(\partial(ru_r)/\partial r) + (\partial u_z/\partial z) = 0. \quad (46)$$

From this relation it follows that radial outflow of fluid is accompanied by a compensating axial inflow. Near the rotating disk, due to the no-slip condition, the azimuthal velocity is formed as $u_\varphi \approx \Omega r$, and the centrifugal term $-u_\varphi^2/r$ in the radial momentum equation produces acceleration directed from the inner region toward the periphery. This leads to the formation of a radial flow $u_r > 0$ in the disk region.

According to the continuity equation (46), such a radial outflow is accompanied by an axial inflow toward the disk. In the presence of the rod, this inflow is formed not on the axis $r = 0$, but in the near-axis annular region $r \gtrsim r_s$, since the inner region is occupied by a solid body. As a result, a primary circulation cell is formed: the fluid descends in the near-axis region, then spreads radially above the disk, rises along the sidewall, and returns toward the inner region in the upper part of the reservoir.

Additional complexity in the flow structure arises due to the tangential inflow, which imposes a nonzero azimuthal velocity:

$$u_\varphi(R, z_{in}) = U_{in}. \quad (47)$$

At the same time, the flow acquires circulation defined as

$$\Gamma = \oint u_\varphi r \, d\varphi = 2\pi r u_\varphi. \quad (48)$$

During the transport of fluid from the wall toward the inner region, the angular momentum is partially conserved, $ru_\varphi \approx Const$, which leads to an increase in the azimuthal velocity with decreasing radius ($u_\varphi \sim 1/r$). This enhances centrifugal effects and generates a radial pressure gradient:

$$\partial p / \partial r = \rho u_\varphi^2 / r \quad (49)$$

As a result, the pressure near the wall exceeds that in the near-axis region, promoting flow redistribution and the formation of additional recirculation zones, particularly in the upper part of the reservoir.

Radial outflow through the side opening creates a localized low-pressure region, $p_{out} < p_{tank}$, forming a pressure gradient $-\nabla p$, directed toward the outlet. Near the discharge opening, the flow is deflected toward the exit, while the remaining fluid continues to participate in the global circulation. The competition between radial outflow and localized suction leads to the appearance of reverse-flow regions and the formation of additional vortex cells, especially in the near-bottom region and in the vicinity of the outlet.

For the analysis of recirculation zones, it is convenient to introduce the stream function $\psi(r, z)$, defined by the relations:

$$\begin{cases} u_r = (1/r)(\partial\psi/\partial z) \\ u_z = -(1/r)(\partial\psi/\partial r) \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

The curves $\psi = Const$ represent streamlines in the meridional plane. A recirculation zone arises in regions where the streamlines are closed, and its center is determined by the conditions $u_r = 0, u_z = 0$ or equivalently, $\partial\psi/\partial r = 0, \partial\psi/\partial z = 0$. The appearance of multiple such critical points is associated with differ-

ences in boundary conditions on the surfaces of the reservoir. In the disk region, radial outflow occurs ($u_r > 0$); at the sidewall, due to the impermeability condition, $u_r = 0$, which causes the flow to turn upward ($u_z > 0$). In the upper part of the reservoir, the flow returns toward the inner region ($u_r < 0$), after which it again descends in the near-axis annular zone ($u_z < 0$). In this way, the primary circulation cell is formed.

The presence of radial outflow through the side opening induces an additional change in the sign of the velocity components in the vicinity of the outlet, leading to the appearance of new critical points of the stream function and the formation of secondary recirculation zones (Figs. 5 and 7).

Additional insight is provided by the analysis of vorticity. The azimuthal component of vorticity is given by

$$\Omega_\varphi = (\partial u_r / \partial z) - (\partial u_z / \partial r) \quad (51)$$

A change in the sign of Ω_φ in different regions of the reservoir indicates the existence of adjacent zones with opposite directions of rotation. Near the disk, the vorticity is determined by the gradient of radial velocity with respect to height; near the sidewall, its sign changes due to flow deceleration and upward deflection; and in the upper region, due to the return flow toward the inner domain.

Thus, the combined action of rotation, inflow, and outflow leads to the formation of a complex multicellular flow structure, including several secondary recirculation zones separated by separatrices. These zones reflect the spatial non-uniformity of the velocity field and confirm the three-dimensional nature of the flow.

The formation of additional zones can also be explained through the pressure balance. Rotation generates a radial pressure distribution:

$$p(r) = p(r_s) + \int_{r_s}^r \rho (u_\varphi^2 / s) \, ds, \quad (52)$$

where the lower limit of integration corresponds to the inner boundary of the flow $r = r_s$, occupied by the rotating rod.

Figure 5. Flow structure in the longitudinal (meridional) section of a cylindrical reservoir with a rotating disk. On the left, the stream function field is shown with superimposed streamlines; the color scale represents the intensity of circulation. In the upper part of the reservoir, a large recirculation zone is formed with maximum values of the stream function, whereas in the central region a secondary closed structure with opposite rotation is observed. Near the disk surface, an intense radial outflow of fluid arises due to centrifugal effects. On the right, streamlines are presented, clearly identifying the boundaries of recirculation zones, separatrices, and transition regions between them. The resulting pattern reflects a complex multicellular flow structure formed by the interaction of radial outflow, axial inflow, and swirl enhanced by the rotation of the disk and the coaxial rod.

In the case of quasi-solid-body rotation ($u_\phi = \Omega r$), one obtains

$$p(r) = p(r_s) + (\rho\Omega^2/2)(r^2 - r_s^2). \quad (53)$$

Thus, the pressure at the wall exceeds that in the inner region:

$$\nabla p_{R \rightarrow r_s} = p(R) - p(r_s) = (\rho\Omega^2/2)(R^2 - r_s^2). \quad (54)$$

This creates a tendency for fluid motion from the high-pressure region near the wall toward the lower-pressure near-axis zone. However, due to rotation and boundary conditions, the motion acquires a circulatory character: near the disk, the fluid spreads radially outward; along the wall, it rises upward; in the upper part of the reservoir, it returns toward the inner region; and then descends again in the annular zone $r \gtrsim r_s$. In the presence of an outlet with reduced pressure,

$$p_{out} < p(R, z), \quad (55)$$

a localized suction region is formed in its vicinity. In this case, part of the flow is directed toward the outlet, while the remaining fluid bypasses the suction region. At the interface between these streams, a separating surface arises on which the velocity direction changes. In the meridional section, this surface corresponds to a separatrix of the stream function: on one side, the fluid is discharged toward the outlet, while on the other, it returns to the circulation cell. In this way, additional recirculation zones are formed.

In terms of dimensionless parameters, the formation of secondary recirculation zones is governed by the relationship between the rotational Reynolds number Re_Ω , the swirl parameter S , and the flow-rate parameter C_Q (28). At low values of Re_Ω , viscous effects suppress the development of secondary vortices, and the flow remains relatively smooth. As Re_Ω increases, inertial and centrifugal effects become dominant, leading to enhanced radial transport and the formation of pronounced recirculation zones. An increase in the swirl parameter S results in higher angular momentum of the flow and a reduction of pressure in the inner region, whereas an increase in the flow-rate parameter C_Q causes deformation of the primary circulation and promotes the formation of additional local vortex cells near the outlet.

Thus, secondary recirculation zones arise when regions with opposite directions of meridional velocity exist within the flow. Mathematically, this is manifested by the appearance of multiple critical points of the stream function

$$\nabla\psi = 0, \quad (56)$$

as well as by a change in the sign of the azimuthal component of vorticity and the formation of separatrices that divide flows directed toward the outlet from those returning into the reservoir volume.

The rotating disk generates radial outflow, the rod enhances swirl in the near-axis annular region, the tangential inflow increases the angular momentum of the flow, and the radial outflow creates a localized low-pressure region. The sidewalls, due to impermeability conditions, force the flow to change direction and close into circulation loops. The combined action of these factors leads to the formation of a complex multicellular flow structure, including closed recirculation zones in the central (annular), sidewall, upper, and near-bottom regions of the reservoir.

8. Conical recirculation zone above the disk.

A localized recirculation zone of conical shape is formed above the surface of the rotating disk, located in the transition region between the downward axial flow and the radial outflow of fluid.

Its formation is due to the interaction of two mechanisms: the radial outflow induced by centrifugal forces near the disk, and the axial inflow of fluid in the near-axis annular region. In the region where these flows intersect, a zone of intense shear arises with elevated velocity gradients, leading to the closure of streamlines and the formation of a local vortex structure.

In the first approximation, this zone may be described as a local perturbation of the stream function:

$$\psi_8(r, z) = A \exp(-[(r - \alpha z)^2 / \sigma_r^2] - [(z - z_0)^2 / \sigma_z^2]), \quad (57)$$

where the parameter α defines the inclination of the generatrix of the conical structure. The corresponding velocity components are determined from the stream function as:

$$\begin{cases} u_r = (1/r)(\partial\psi_8/\partial z) \\ u_z = -(1/r)(\partial\psi_8/\partial r) \end{cases} \quad (58)$$

The conical recirculation zone acts as a transition region in which momentum is redistributed between axial and radial motion. It serves as a source of local vorticity amplification and represents the initial region for the formation of tertiary vortex structures propagating along separatrices between the primary recirculation zones.

In the presence of a coaxial rotating rod, the structure of this zone acquires an annular character: the apex of the vortex region is formed not on the axis $r = 0$, but near the inner boundary $r \approx r_s$. This leads to a displacement of the zone and a modification of its geometry compared to the classical axisymmetric case.

In a real system, the shape of this zone deviates from axisymmetry under the influence of tangential inflow and radial outflow of fluid. This results in a displacement of the vortex axis and deformation of its geometry; however, the overall formation mechanism remains unchanged.

9. Exchange between primary and secondary recirculation zones.

The exchange between recirculation zones and the main flow in a rotating reservoir is governed by the Navier–Stokes equations and is determined by the continuity of the velocity field, momentum transport, and vorticity diffusion. Viscosity and shear stresses play a key role in this process. The global flow structure is defined by the main flow paths, including axial transport, radial outflow, and return motion along the walls. Recirculation zones are regions with closed streamlines, separated from the main flow by separatrices. However, due to viscosity, these zones are not completely isolated and remain in continuous exchange with the surrounding flow.

In an ideal inviscid fluid, streamlines coincide with particle trajectories, and the boundaries between zones are material surfaces. In a viscous fluid, this condition is violated, since the shear stresses

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu(\partial u_i / \partial x_j) \quad (59)$$

ensure momentum transfer across the boundaries of the zones.

In the vicinity of separatrices, shear layers are formed in which significant velocity gradients are observed,

$$\partial u / \partial n \neq 0, \quad (60)$$

where n is the normal to the interface. These regions act as zones of intense exchange, since viscosity induces momentum diffusion. The corresponding process is described by the momentum equation

$$\rho (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \mu \Delta \mathbf{u}. \quad (61)$$

where the term $\mu \Delta \mathbf{u}$ represents viscous transport of momentum. The energy exchange is characterized by the kinetic energy balance equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial(u^2/2)/\partial t + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla (u^2/2) = \\ = -(1/\rho) \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla p + \nu \mathbf{u} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{u}. \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

The last term can be expressed in the form

$$\nu \mathbf{u} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{u} = -\nu |\nabla \mathbf{u}|^2 + \nu \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} \nabla \mathbf{u}), \quad (63)$$

which shows that part of the energy is dissipated, while another part is transported across the boundaries of the zones.

An important role is also played by vorticity transport, described by the equation

$$D\Omega/Dt = (\Omega \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} + \nu \Delta \Omega. \quad (64)$$

The diffusive term $\nu \Delta \Omega$ leads to the ‘‘smearing’’ of vortex structures and their penetration across the boundaries of recirculation zones. In regions with large velocity gradients, an intense exchange of vorticity occurs between the main flow and vortex cells.

In the system under consideration, this exchange is enhanced by the presence of a coaxial rotating rod, which forms an additional shear layer in the near-axis region $r \approx r_s$, as well as by tangential inflow and radial outflow, which create spatial non-uniformity in the pressure and velocity fields.

The nature of this exchange is determined by the ratio of convective to diffusive transport, characterized by the Reynolds number:

$$Re = UL/\nu. \quad (65)$$

At high values of Re , convection dominates, the boundaries of recirculation zones become sharper, and the exchange is localized within thin shear layers. At low Re , viscosity smooths the gradients, leading to blurred boundaries and enhanced exchange.

In practice, the exchange proceeds as follows: the main flow, moving along the global circulation, generates velocity gradients at the boundary of a recirculation zone. Viscosity transports momentum into the zone, sustaining circulation within it, while part of the fluid from the zone returns to the main flow through regions where streamlines converge and the pressure gradient changes sign. This process is accompanied by energy dissipation:

$$\varepsilon = \nu |\nabla \mathbf{u}|^2. \quad (66)$$

Thus, recirculation zones represent open dynamic structures that are in continuous exchange with the main flow. Their existence and stability are determined by the balance between convective transport, viscous diffusion, and energy dissipation.

In multicellular flows, in addition to primary and secondary recirculation zones, more complex spatial vortex structures are formed, which in the present work are referred to as tertiary vortices.

10. Tertiary vortex as a spatial structure.

In contrast to secondary recirculation zones, a tertiary vortex represents a three-dimensional spatial structure distributed throughout the volume and formed as a system of spiral layers. It can be interpreted as a hollow conical multilayer vortex shell, localized along the separatrices of recirculation zones and forming around the central rotating rod. Each layer of this structure corresponds to an individual separatrix or a region of sharp vorticity variation, which gives the vortex its multilayer character. In a cylindrical reservoir of radius R and height H with a rotating disk of radius b , the tertiary vortex is formed as a spatial layered (quasi-developable) structure with a thickened base near the disk and narrowing with distance from it. The vortex geometry is defined by the radius of the vortex shell, varying with height:

$$r_v(z) = r_s + (b - r_s)(1 - (z/H))^n, \quad (67)$$

where r_s is the rod radius and $n > 1$ is a parameter controlling the thickening of the vortex near the disk. If a more general approximation is required, the expression

$$r_v(z) = r_s + r_{min} + (r_{max} - r_{min})(1 - (z/H))^n \quad (68)$$

can be used.

The asymmetry of the hollow tertiary vortex structure, caused by radial outflow of fluid, is taken into account by introducing an angular dependence.

$$r_v(z, \theta) = r_v(z)[1 + \varepsilon \cos(\theta - \theta_0)], \quad r_v > r_s. \quad (69)$$

where $\varepsilon \ll 1$, and θ_0 denotes the direction of the outflow. The velocity field within the vortex may be represented as

$$\begin{cases} u_r \approx U_0(1 - (z/H))(1 - (r_s^2/r^2)), \\ u_\phi \approx \Omega r \exp(-z/\delta), \\ u_z \approx -W_0(1 - (r_s^2/r^2)) \exp(-(r - r_s)^2/r_v^2(z)), \end{cases} \quad (70)$$

which reflects the combined action of radial outflow, azimuthal rotation, and axial inflow. The spiral structure of the vortex (motion along layers) is determined by the kinematic relation

$$d\phi/dz = u_\phi/r_v u_z, \quad (71)$$

which, on the surface of the vortex shell $r = r_v(z)$, takes the form

$$d\phi/dz = u_\phi/r_v(z) u_z \quad (72)$$

Under the approximation $u_\phi \approx \Omega r$, we obtain

$$d\phi/dz \approx \Omega/u_z, \quad (73)$$

which shows that the pitch of the spiral is determined by the ratio between rotation and axial transport.

The axial vorticity is defined as

$$\zeta = (1/r)(\partial(r u_\phi)/\partial r) \quad (74)$$

and, taking into account the variation of the vortex radius (deformation), it can be estimated as

$$\zeta(z) \sim \zeta_0(r_{max}/r_v(z))^2 \quad (75)$$

which corresponds to vorticity amplification as the structure contracts due to vortex-line stretching.

The surface of the vortex shell of the tertiary vortex is defined by the function

$$\Phi(r, \theta, z) = r - r_v(z) = 0, \quad r > r_s \quad (76)$$

and the condition of its transport by the flow, $D\Phi/Dt = 0$, leads to the kinematic relation

$$u_r - (dr_v/dz)u_z = 0, \quad (77)$$

which, in the presence of asymmetry, generalizes to

$$u_r - (\partial r_v / \partial z) u_z - (1/r)(\partial r_v / \partial \theta) u_\phi = 0. \quad (78)$$

The thickness of the vortex layers is estimated as

$$\delta(z) \sim \sqrt{\nu/\Omega} + \alpha[r_v(z) - r_s], \quad (79)$$

which reflects the thickening of the structure near the disk and its contraction with increasing height. Thus, the tertiary vortex represents a deformed hollow conical multilayer vortex shell with an asymmetric axis and variable layer swirl, formed under the action of centrifugal outflow, axial inflow, and local pressure gradients.

The presence of a central rod fundamentally alters the vortex structure: it forms not around the axis $r = 0$, but around the inner boundary $r = r_s$, resulting in a

hollow vortex shell. In the region $0 \leq r < r_s$, motion is absent, and on the rod surface the no-slip and impermeability conditions are satisfied:

$$u_r = 0, \quad u_z = 0, \quad u_\phi = \Omega r_s. \quad (80)$$

Thus, the rod suppresses the formation of an axial jet, redistributes the flow into the annular region, and leads to the transformation of the tertiary vortex from a solid structure into a hollow spiral shell with asymmetric geometry. It should be noted that the proposed model of the tertiary vortex (Fig. 6) is approximate in nature and reflects the qualitative flow structure consistent with the Navier–Stokes equations, but does not represent their exact analytical solution.

Figure 6. Tertiary vortex as a three-dimensional multilayer spiral structure formed in a system with a rotating disk and a coaxial rod. The vortex has a hollow conical shape with a thickened base near the disk and narrowing with increasing height. Its structure is asymmetric with respect to the axis of rotation and is localized along the separatrices of recirculation zones. Unlike classical axisymmetric vortices, the vortex considered here represents a deformed spatial shell with variable swirl, formed as a result of the interaction of radial outflow, axial inflow, and local pressure gradients caused by fluid outflow.

11. Discussion. Comparative dynamics of vortex formation in related system. The flow considered in a cylindrical reservoir with a rotating disk, tangential inflow, and radial outflow exhibits several features common to classical problems of vortex formation in rotating fluid volumes with drainage. Despite differences in geometry and boundary conditions, these systems share a common mechanism of vortex generation associated with the transport and stretching of vorticity in the presence of radial flow and an axial pressure gradient.

In the system with a rotating disk, vortex motion is generated by the transfer of angular momentum from the disk to the fluid and the subsequent radial outflow, which induces a compensating axial inflow. In systems without a disk but with a rotating fluid volume and drainage, a similar radial transport is formed within Ekman boundary layer. Despite the difference in mechanisms, in both cases vorticity is transported toward regions of reduced pressure and subsequently amplified due to vortex-line stretching.

Additional insight into the flow structure is provided by comparison with the classical von Kármán solution [1]. In that problem, the flow near an infinite rotating disk in an unbounded quiescent fluid admits a self-similar solution describing radial outflow, axial inflow, and decay of swirl with distance from the disk. In the present study, this structure is preserved only in the vicinity of the disk surface and may be interpreted as a local asymptotic behavior of the flow. However, the finite size of the reservoir, the presence of sidewalls, and

the inlet and outlet conditions lead to the breakdown of self-similarity and the formation of a substantially more complex three-dimensional flow field.

A more detailed understanding of the formation of recirculation flows in a cylindrical reservoir with a rotating disk and rod is provided by the analysis of the regime diagram, which makes it possible to establish the relationship between the rotational Reynolds number Re_Ω , the swirl parameter S , the dimensionless radial outflow intensity C_Q (28), and the processes of shear-layer instability leading to the formation of complex three-dimensional vortex structures (Fig. 7).

The regime diagram shows that the flow evolution is governed by the competition between viscous diffusion, centrifugal transport of angular momentum, tangential swirl injection, and localized pressure gradients arising due to radial fluid outflow.

At low values of the rotational Reynolds number Re_Ω and weak swirl intensity S viscous effects dominate and suppress the formation of secondary structures. In this regime, the flow remains nearly axisymmetric and is characterized by a single global meridional circulation cell. The streamlines are smooth, and perturbations decay rapidly due to viscous dissipation. The characteristic balance in this region may be estimated by the condition $\nu/R^2 \gg \Omega$ or $Re_\Omega \gg 1$, which corresponds to the dominance of viscous diffusion over rotational transport.

As the swirl parameter increases, the balance between centrifugal forces and viscous diffusion changes.

The primary circulation loses stability, and additional recirculation zones appear in the meridional plane. These regions are separated by separatrices along which intense shear layers are formed. The emergence of such layers corresponds to the transition from Regime I to Regime II in the regime diagram. The critical points of the meridional flow are determined by the condition

$$\nabla\psi = 0, \tag{81}$$

where $\psi(r, z)$ is the stream function of the axisymmetric circulation.

A further increase in the swirl parameter and the

rotational Reynolds number leads to the destabilization of the separatrix surfaces themselves. In this regime, localized maxima of axial vorticity arise, and spiral structures develop in transverse cross-sections of the reservoir. The axial vorticity is defined as

$$\Omega_z = (\partial u_y / \partial x) - (\partial u_x / \partial y). \tag{82}$$

These structures correspond to the formation of tertiary vortices and represent the first stage of three-dimensional breakdown of axial symmetry. Unlike classical compact vortex cores, the tertiary vortex in the present system develops as a distributed annular spiral structure surrounding the rotating rod.

Figure 7. Flow regime diagram in a cylindrical reservoir with a rotating disk, rod, tangential inlet and radial outlet (Transitions between the regimes are governed by the competition between viscous dissipation, centrifugal transport of angular momentum, flow swirl, and localized pressure reduction in the fluid outflow region).

The spiral modulation of the tertiary vortex may be represented in the form

$$\Omega_z(r, \varphi, z, t) = \Omega_0(r, z) + A(r, z) \cos(m\varphi - \omega t + \beta z), \tag{83}$$

where m is the azimuthal mode number, β is the axial spiral pitch parameter, and ω is the precession frequency of the spiral structure. A more detailed analysis of the spatial modes governing the helical structure of swirling flow in a cylindrical reservoir with a stationary central rod is presented in the work of Milyute & Milyus [18].

The regime diagram also demonstrates that the transition toward tertiary vortex formation strongly depends on the interaction between tangential inflow and radial fluid outflow. The radial outlet creates a localized low-pressure region that bends streamlines toward the sidewall and enhances azimuthal shear. The characteristic pressure gradient in this case may be estimated as

$$\partial p / \partial r \sim \rho u_\theta^2 / r. \tag{84}$$

This mechanism shifts the instability threshold toward lower values of Re_Ω compared with the classical problem of a rotating disk in a closed volume.

An important feature of the considered system is that the tertiary vortex develops within a relatively thin shear layer surrounding the separatrix surfaces. If the layer thickness satisfies the condition $\delta_s \ll R$,

the vorticity becomes concentrated within a narrow spiral-conical region rather than forming separate volumetric vortex cells. In this case, the vortex structure behaves as a single coherent spiral shell whose transverse cross-section appears as a continuous spiral pattern.

In the region of large values of Re_Ω , S and C_Q , the flow transitions into a complex unsteady vortex regime. In this state, spiral structures lose coherence, multiple interacting recirculation zones appear, and the flow exhibits features of quasi-turbulent behavior. The boundaries between individual vortex regions become strongly deformed, and processes of local vortex merging and breakdown may occur.

An important result of the present study is that the tertiary vortex regime occupies an intermediate position between stable axisymmetric circulation and fully disordered vortex motion. Thus, the tertiary vortex should be interpreted not as a random local instability, but as an organized stage of spatial flow restructuring associated with the progressive destabilization of separatrix shear layers.

Therefore, the transition boundaries in the regime diagram should not be interpreted as strict critical curves, but rather as finite transition regions whose location is determined by the combined influence of ro-

tation, inflow swirl, viscous diffusion, and pressure gradients arising in the radial outflow region.

Table 1.

Comparison of the classical von Kármán solution and the proposed flow model in a cylindrical reservoir with a rotating disk and a coaxial rod.

Feature	von Kármán Model	Proposed Model
Geometry	Infinite rotating disk	Bounded cylindrical vessel
Boundaries	None (unbounded fluid)	Side wall, bottom, top lid
Inner boundary	None	Rotating shaft (core), $r=r_s$
Flow type	Axisymmetric	Three-dimensional, asymmetric
Self-similarity	Exists	Broken (locally valid near disk)
Radial flow	Outward from axis	Outward in annular zone $r \gtrsim r_s$
Axial structure	Inflow toward axis	Inflow in near-shaft annular zone
Swirl source	Disk only	Disk + shaft + tangential inlet
Recirculation zones	None	Multi-cell structure (9 zones)
Separatrices	None	Present
Secondary flows	Weak	Well developed
Tertiary vortex	Absent	Forms (multi-layer structure)
Pressure	Determined locally	Determined by global flow structure
Outlet influence	None	Deforms flow, asymmetry ϵ
Primary regime	Boundary layer	Global circulation + local layers

A key distinguishing feature of the configuration under consideration is the presence of a coaxial rotating rod (kern). Its presence significantly modifies the flow structure in the near-axis region: the formation of an axial jet in the region $r \rightarrow r_s$, is suppressed, the flow acquires an annular character, and the angular momentum distribution becomes more uniform. As a result, the rotating rod (kern) modifies the distribution of velocity gradients and reduces the sharpness of the boundaries between recirculation zones, partially smoothing the structures associated with different circulation cells.

In contrast to the classical von Kármán problem, where the flow remains single-celled and does not contain closed recirculation regions, the present system exhibits a multicellular structure, including several recirculation zones separated by separatrices. These zones interact both with each other and with the main flow, forming a complex spatial organization.

Thus, the flow model in a reservoir with a rotating disk and a core may be regarded as a generalization of the von Kármán solution to the case of confined geometry with an internal rotating boundary and external sources and sinks of momentum. This generalization makes it possible to describe the formation of multi-level vortex structures, including tertiary vortices arising from the interaction between global circulation and local shear regions.

This similarity allows the use of results obtained for draining flows in rotating reservoirs, as well as the classical von Kármán solution, to interpret vortex dynamics in the present system. It is shown that the vortex circulation increases over time and reaches a quasi-steady value on a characteristic timescale determined by viscosity and system geometry. Despite differences in the sources of rotation, the resulting vortex structure is characterized by the concentration of vorticity in a confined region, the formation of an annular core, and

a complex system of recirculation zones. Comparison with the classical von Kármán solution shows that, in the present problem, the flow structure becomes significantly more complex due to the finite geometry of the reservoir, the presence of a coaxial rotating rod, as well as fluid inflow and outflow. While in the von Kármán model the flow is described by a single self-similar structure without closed regions, the system considered here exhibits a multicellular flow with pronounced recirculation zones separated by separatrices. Thus, the confined geometry of the reservoir, the presence of the rotating rod, and the interaction between fluid inflow and outflow lead to a qualitatively new type of multicellular swirling flow that cannot be described within the framework of the classical self-similar von Kármán theory.

The boundaries between the indicated recirculation zones correspond to separatrix surfaces characterized by elevated velocity gradients and concentrated vorticity. Thin shear layers are formed along these surfaces, and the loss of stability of these layers leads to the emergence of three-dimensional spiral structures. This mechanism is considered to be the basis for tertiary vortex formation in the investigated system.

Figure 8 shows that the flow structure in the longitudinal (meridional) section of the rotating reservoir with a disk, constructed based on the stream function field and streamlines. The coordinate axes correspond to the radial direction r and the axial direction z . The streamlines form both closed and open trajectories, reflecting the presence of several stable recirculation zones, each highlighted by color and numbered.

In the upper part of the reservoir, a large recirculation zone (zone 1) is formed, representing a closed vortex with its center located around $z \approx 0.4$. It is associated with the return motion of fluid from the wall toward the inner region and is characterized by a rela-